

OPTIMAL STACKING SEQUENCE OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES FOR MAXIMUM AXIAL BUCKLING LOAD

T.Y. Kam and K.H. Chu
Department of Mechanical Engineering
National Chiao Tung University
Hsin Chu 30050, Taiwan , R.O.C.

ABSTRACT

The optimal lamination arrangement of thick composite laminates for maximum axial buckling load is studied via a multi-level multi-start global optimization technique. A shear deformable finite element has been adopted for the buckling analysis of the laminates during the optimal design process. The optimal layer orientations and thicknesses for the laminates with maximum axial buckling loads are designed via the optimization techniques which has proved to be efficient and effective in designing thick laminated composite plates. A number of examples of the design of symmetrically and antisymmetrically laminated composite plates with various material properties, side-to-thickness ratios and aspect ratios are given to illustrate the practical applications of the present method.

Keywords: Laminates, Optimum Design, Buckling, Shear Deformation, Finite Element

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, optimal design of laminated composite plates subject to compressive load has become an important subject of research. A vast proportion of the published work, however, is limited to simple thin plates consisting of very few layers and subjected to no transverse shear deformation. For instance, the optimal design of laminated composite plates with the consideration of buckling in [1-4] were composed of four layers and based on the classical plate theory. Furthermore, in the previous work only either layer orientations or layer thicknesses were treated as design variables. It has been shown [5] that the transverse shear deformation may have significant effects on the behavior of thick laminated composite plates due to the thickness effect and the low transverse shear modulus relative to the in-plane Young's moduli. Since stability analysis of laminated composite plates is an important consideration in designing such structures, a reliable prediction of the buckling loads of the plates requires the use of shear deformable theories. On the other hand, laminated composite plates may be made up of many layers of different orientations and even a relatively simple composite plate may possess many design variables (layer orientations and thicknesses). The increase in the number of design variables when coupled with the highly nonlinear way in which buckling load vary with changes in fiber orientation and layer thickness can result in great difficulties in obtaining convergence to a local minimum when conventional optimization techniques, used by previous researchers, are employed. Therefore, if more realistic and better results of the optimal design of laminated composite plates are desired, the effect of transverse shear deformation must be included and more efficient and reliable global optimization techniques be used. This paper presents a procedure for the optimal design of laminated composite plates for maximum axial buckling load. The buckling analysis of laminated composite plates is performed by a simple yet accurate shear deformable finite element method. A multi-level

multi-start global optimization technique is proposed to design both layer orientations and layer thicknesses for maximizing the axial buckling load of laminated plates. The proposed optimization procedure is then used to design thick symmetrically and antisymmetrically laminated composite plates for maximum axial buckling load. Optimal layups are determined for the plates with various side-to-thickness ratios, aspect ratios and material properties.

2. LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATE ANALYSIS

The finite element method will be used to perform the buckling analysis of laminated composite plates. Consider a rectangular plate of area $a \times b$ and constant thickness h subject to in-plane force in static equilibrium as shown in Fig. 1. The introduction of virtual displacements δu_i to the plate gives the virtual work equation as [8]

$$\frac{1}{2} \delta \int_V (\sigma_{ij} \epsilon_{ij}) dv + \frac{1}{2} \delta \int_V (\sigma_{ij}^0 u_{s,i} u_{s,j}) dv = 0 \quad (1a)$$

or in matrix form

$$\frac{1}{2} \delta \int_V \underline{\epsilon}^T \underline{\sigma} dv + \frac{1}{2} \delta \int_V (\sigma_x^0 \underline{u}_{,x}^T \underline{u}_{,x}) dv = 0 \quad (1b)$$

where σ_{ij} , ϵ_{ij} represent stress and strain components, respectively; σ_{ij}^0 denotes initial stress components; v is the volume of the plate; and the subscript comma denotes the partial derivative. In eqn(1b) all initial stress components except the one in x -direction are assumed to be zeros; the first term denotes the virtual work done by virtual stresses and the second term the virtual work done by initial stresses. The displacement field is assumed to be of the following form:

$$u_1 = u_0(x,y) + z \psi_x(x,y) \quad ; \quad u_2 = v_0(x,y) + z \psi_y(x,y) \quad ; \quad u_3 = w(x,y) \quad (2)$$

where u_0 and v_0 are the in-plane displacements of the middle plane of the plate; ψ_x , ψ_y are the shear rotations; and w is the transverse deflection. The plate constitutive equations can be written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \\ Q_y \\ Q_x \\ N_6 \\ M_1 \\ M_2 \\ M_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & 0 & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & 0 & 0 & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ 0 & 0 & A_{44} & A_{45} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{45} & A_{55} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & 0 & 0 & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & 0 & 0 & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & 0 & 0 & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & 0 & 0 & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_0, x \\ v_0, y \\ w, y + \psi_y \\ w, x + \psi_x \\ u_0, y + v_0, x \\ \psi_x, x \\ \psi_y, y \\ \psi_x, y + \psi_y, x \end{bmatrix} \quad (3a)$$

or in matrix form

$$\underline{N} = \underline{C} \underline{u}' \quad (3b)$$

where N_1, N_2, \dots, M_6 are stress resultants; and material components A_{ij} , B_{ij} , and D_{ij} are given by

$$(A_{ij}, B_{ij}, D_{ij}) = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} Q_{ij}^{(m)}(1, z, z^2) dz, \quad (i, j=1, 2, 6)$$

and

$$A_{ij} = k_{\alpha} \cdot k_{\beta} \cdot \bar{A}_{ij}, \quad \bar{A}_{ij} = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} Q_{ij}^{(m)} dz \quad (4)$$

$$(\alpha = 6 - i, \beta = 6 - j), \quad (i, j = 4, 5)$$

The virtual work equation of the plate discretized into n elements can be written as

$$\frac{1}{2} \delta \sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \int_{v_e} \underline{\epsilon}^T \underline{\sigma} dv + \int_{v_e} (\sigma_x^0 \underline{u}_{,x}^T) dv \right\}_k = 0 \quad (5)$$

where v_e is volume of an element. The mid-plane displacements ($u_0, v_0, w, \psi_x, \psi_y$) within an element are given as functions of $5 \times q$ discrete nodal displacements and in matrix form they are expressed as

$$\underline{u} = \sum_{i=1}^q [H_i \underline{I}] \underline{v}_{ie} = \underline{H} \underline{v}_e \quad (6)$$

where q is the number of nodes for the element; H_i are shape functions; \underline{I} is a 5×5 unit matrix; \underline{H} is shape function matrix; and the nodal displacements \underline{v}_{ie} are

$$\underline{v}_{ie} = \{ u_{0i}, v_{0i}, w_i, \psi_{xi}, \psi_{yi} \}^T \quad (i=1, \dots, q) \quad (7)$$

Substituting eqn(6) into eqn(5) with the observation of the stress-strain and strain-displacement relations, one gets

$$\frac{1}{2} \delta \sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \int_{A_e} (\underline{B} \underline{v}_e)^T \underline{C} \underline{B} \underline{v}_e dv - \int_{A_e} \underline{N}_1 (\underline{H}_{,x} \underline{v}_e)^T (\underline{H}_{,x} \underline{v}_e) dv \right\}_k = 0 \quad (8)$$

where A_e is midplane area of an element, \underline{B} is the matrix containing the derivatives of shape functions, and \underline{N}_1 is the initial compressive stress resultant in x -direction. Using the standard finite element assembling procedure, eqn(8) can be written as

$$\frac{1}{2} \delta \left[\underline{v}^T \sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \int_{A_e} \underline{a}^T \underline{B}^T \underline{C} \underline{B} \underline{a} dv \right\}_k \underline{v} - \underline{v}^T \sum_{k=1}^n \left\{ \int_{A_e} \underline{N}_1 \underline{a}^T \underline{H}_{,x} \underline{H}_{,x} \underline{a} dv \right\}_k \underline{v} \right] = 0 \quad (9)$$

where \underline{a} is the congruent transformation matrix.

After performing the assembling process, the above equation becomes

$$\delta \underline{v}^T [\underline{K} \underline{v} - \lambda \underline{K}_g \underline{v}] = 0 \quad (10)$$

where \underline{K} , \underline{K}_g , \underline{v} , λ are the generalized stiffness matrix, geometric stiffness matrix, displacement vector of the plate and load factor, respectively. The equilibrium equations of the finite element model of the plate can be obtained as

$$\underline{K} \underline{v} - \lambda \underline{K}_g \underline{v} = 0 \quad (11)$$

In this study, a quadratic (q=8) element of the serendipity family with reduced integration of 2x2 Gauss rule is used. The shear correction factors in eqn(4) can be determined, respectively, by the following expressions [6]:

$$k_1^2 = \left[A_{55} \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} g_1^{(m)}(z) dz \right]^{-1} \quad (12a)$$

and

$$k_2^2 = \left[A_{44} \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} g_2^{(m)}(z) dz \right]^{-1} \quad (12b)$$

in which

$$g_1^{(m)} = S_{55}^{(m)} [a^{(m)} + Q_{11}^{(m)} \cdot z(2B_{11} - A_{11}z)/2D]^2 \quad (13a)$$

and

$$g_2^{(m)} = S_{44}^{(m)} [a^{(m)} + Q_{22}^{(m)} \cdot z(2B_{22} - A_{22}z)/2D]^2 \quad (13b)$$

where

$$D = (D_{11}A_{11} - B_{11}^2) \quad (13c)$$

In eqn(13), $a^{(m)}$ are constants determined from interface continuity conditions and the requirement that transverse shear stress vanish on the bottom surface of the plate; $S_{44}^{(m)}$ and $S_{55}^{(m)}$ are the shear compliances. It has been found that the use of the above shear correction factors in the buckling analysis of laminated composite plates can yield very good results.

3. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The objective in the optimal design of a laminated composite plate with given plate thickness h and number of layers NL is the selection of layer orientations and thicknesses which give the maximum buckling load of the plate. In mathematical form the optimization problem is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Minimize} \quad & \Phi(\underline{\theta}, \underline{h}) = - \sum_{i=1}^n \eta_i (\lambda_i / \lambda_i^0) \\ \text{Subject to} \quad & 0^\circ \leq \theta_i \leq 180^\circ \\ & \sum_{i=1}^{NL} h_i = h \\ & h_i \geq 0 \quad (i=1, \dots, NL) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where Φ is a multi-objective function; $\underline{\theta} = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{NL})^T$ the vector of ply orientations; h_i is the thickness of the i th ply; λ_i is the buckling load of the i th mode; λ_i^0 is the reference values of λ_i , and η_i is weighting factor.

The direct solution of the above optimization problem may become intractable due to the fact that the gradient of the objective function is almost completely controlled by layer thicknesses, which can lead to the repeated violation of the constraints on thicknesses and thus the divergence of the solution. To circumvent this difficulty, the original optimization problem will be solved via a two-level optimization approach. At the first level of optimization, the layer thicknesses are kept constant and the conditional global

optimal layer orientations are determined to maximize the buckling strength of the plate using the multi-start global optimization method presented in [9]. At the second level of optimization, the optimal layer orientations obtained in the previous level of optimization are kept unaltered and the conditional global optimal layer thicknesses are designed, using the same multi-start global optimization method, to minimize the augmented Lagrangian made up of plate buckling strength and the constraints on layer and plate thicknesses. The two-level optimization problem can be expressed in the following mathematical form as:

(i) First-level optimization

$$\text{minimize } \Phi(\underline{\theta}|\underline{h}) = -\sum_{i=1}^N \xi_i \lambda_i \quad \text{with respect to } \underline{\theta} \quad (15)$$

(ii) Second-level optimization

$$\text{minimize } \Psi(\underline{h}|\underline{\theta}) = -\sum_{i=1}^N \xi_i \lambda_i + \sum_{j=1}^{NL} [\alpha_j \psi_j + \gamma_p \psi_j^2] + [\alpha_{NL+1} P(\underline{h}) + \gamma_p P(\underline{h})^2] \quad \text{with respect to } \underline{h} \quad (16)$$

where $\psi_j = \max[g_j(\underline{h}), \frac{-\alpha_j}{2\gamma_p}]$; $g_j(\underline{h}) =$ side constraints for layer thicknesses
 $P(\underline{h}) =$ constraint on plate thickness ; $\alpha_j =$ Lagrange multipliers
 $\gamma_p =$ a multiplier

The update formulas for the Lagrange multipliers are

$$\alpha_j^{p+1} = \alpha_j^p + 2\gamma_p \left\{ \max[g_j(\underline{h}), \frac{-\alpha_j}{2\gamma_p}] \right\} \quad j=1, \dots, NL \quad (17)$$

and

$$\alpha_{NL+1}^{p+1} = \alpha_{NL+1}^p + 2\gamma_p H(\underline{h}) \quad (18)$$

The global optimal solution is then obtained by iterating solutions between the two levels of optimization. The basic idea of the multi-start global optimization method used in the above two levels of optimization is to solve the problem of unconstrained minimization of a differentiable objective function $F(\underline{x})$, $\underline{x} \in \underline{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and $F \in C^1$, with several local minima \hat{F}_j

and corresponding local minimizers \hat{x}_j . It is noted that, for example, in the first level of optimal design of laminated composite plates, \underline{x} and $F(\underline{x})$ become $\underline{\theta}$ and $\Phi(\underline{\theta})$, respectively.

In the global minimization process, a series of starting points are selected at random from the region of interest and a local minimization algorithm is used from each starting point. The search trajectories used by the local minimization algorithm are derived from the equation of motion of a particle of unit mass in an n-dimensional conservative force field, where the potential energy of the particle is represented by $F(\underline{x}(t))$. In such a field the total energy of the particle, consisting of its potential and kinetic energy, is conserved. The motion of the particle is simulated and by monitoring its kinetic energy an interfering strategy is adopted which ensures that the potential energy is systematically reduced. In this way the particle is forced to follow a trajectory towards a local minimum in potential energy at \hat{x} . By uninterrupted the motion of the particle with conserved total energy, other lower local minima including in particular the global minimum are obtained and recorded when the particle is traveling along its path. The motion of the particle is stopped once a termination criterion is satisfied. The same procedure is applied to the other starting points. As the process of searching for the global minimum continues, a Bayesian argument [7] is used to establish the probability of the current overall minimum value of F being the global minimum, given the number of starts and the number of times this value has been achieved. The multi-start procedure is terminated once a target probability, typically 0.998, has been exceeded.

4. EXAMPLES

The forementioned optimization technique will be applied to the design of simply supported symmetrically or antisymmetrically laminated rectangular plates for maximum buckling load of the first mode. The material properties used in the following optimum design are given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Material I : } & E_1/E_2 = 40, G_{12}/E_2 = 0.6, G_{23}/E_2 = 0.5, \nu_{12} = 0.25 \\ \text{Material II : } & E_1/E_2 = 25, G_{12}/E_2 = 0.5, G_{23}/E_2 = 0.2, \nu_{12} = 0.25 \end{aligned}$$

It is assumed that $G_{13}=G_{12}$ and $\nu_{13}=\nu_{12}$. The weighting factors in eqn(15) are zero except η_1 which is set to be 1.0. The optimal stacking sequences of the plates composed of four layers with different thicknesses are evaluated for various material properties, side-to-thickness ratios, and aspect ratios. Table 1 shows the optimal layouts of symmetrically laminated composite plates ($a/b=1.0$) with either ply angles treated as design variables ($h_1=h/NL$) or both ply angles and layer thicknesses as design variables. The optimal solutions for plates of $a/b=2.0$ are given in table 2. It is noted that aspect ratio (a/b) has significant effects on the optimal values of the ply angles of the plates while material properties only have slight effects. In particular, aspect ratio (a/b) has greater effects on the optimal ply angles of thick plates than those of thin plates. For instance, for moderately thick plates ($a/h=10$) the optimal ply angles decrease drastically for aspect ratio from 1.0 to 2.0 while the corresponding optimal ply angles change slightly for thinner plates ($a/h=50$). On the other hand, layer thickness ratio (h_1/h_2) has important effects on buckling load. Tables 3 and 4 illustrate the optimal layouts of antisymmetrically laminated plates of aspect ratios $a/b=1.0$ and 2.0, respectively, with various material properties and side-to-thickness ratios. Again the results listed in the tables show the effects of material properties, side-to-thickness ratio, layer thickness ratio and aspect ratio on the optimal ply orientations and buckling load of the plates. In particular, the layer thickness ratio has greater effects on buckling load for plates with side-to-thickness ratio $a/h=10$ than those of $a/h=30$ and also for plates of material I than those of material II.

5. CONCLUSION

Optimal lamination arrangements of thick laminated composite plates designed for maximum buckling load have been investigated via a shear deformable finite element and a multi-level multi-start global optimization technique. The proposed optimal design algorithm can yield global optimal ply orientations and thicknesses in a very effective way. Results for symmetric and antisymmetric multi-layer plates of various material properties, aspect ratios and side-to-thickness ratios are obtained. It has been shown that the design parameters do have effects of certain degree on the optimal lamination arrangements of laminated composite plates. The results presented in this paper should be valuable to practicing engineers as well as researchers working in this area.

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REFERENCES

1. Hirano, Y., Optimum Design of Laminated Plates under Axial Compression, J. AIAA., Vol. 17, pp. 1017-1019, 1979.
2. Muc, A., Optimal Fibre Orientation for Simply Supported, Angle-ply Plates under Biaxial Compression, Comp. Struct., Vol. 9, pp. 161-172, 1988.

Table 1. Optimum design of symmetrically laminated plates ($a/b=1.0$) for maximum normalized buckling load, $\bar{N}=\bar{N}_1 b^2/E_2 h^3$

Material	$\frac{a}{h}$	Design Variables: Θ			Design Variables: Θ & h		
		Θ	$h_1:h_2$	\bar{N}	Θ	$h_1:h_2$	\bar{N}
I	10	[41/-41]s	1:1	30.50	[39/-42]s	1:3	38.39
	30	[45/-45]s	1:1	47.27	[45/-45]s	1:3	61.91
	50	[45/-45]s	1:1	50.19	[45/-45]s	1:3	65.11
II	10	[41/-41]s	1:1	19.86	[41/-41]s	1:3	24.45
	30	[45/-45]s	1:1	30.72	[45/-45]s	1:3	39.17

Table 2. Optimum design of symmetrically laminated plates ($a/b=2.0$) for maximum normalized buckling load, $\bar{N}=\bar{N}_1 b^2/E_2 h^3$

Material	$\frac{a}{h}$	Design Variables: Θ			Design Variables: Θ & h		
		Θ	$h_1:h_2$	\bar{N}	Θ	$h_1:h_2$	\bar{N}
I	10	[21/-24]s	1:1	12.59	[7/-19]s	1:3	13.00
	30	[33/-35]s	1:1	45.03	[33/-33]s	1:3	53.66
	50	[35/-49]s	1:1	56.40	[35/-45]s	1:3	67.64
II	10	[21/-17]s	1:1	9.43	[16/-3]s	1:3	9.77
	30	[33/-37]s	1:1	30.57	[33/-33]s	1:3	34.12

Table 3. Optimum design of antisymmetrically laminated plates ($a/b=1.0$) for maximum normalized buckling load, $\bar{N}=\bar{N}_1 b^2/E_2 h^3$

Material	$\frac{a}{h}$	Design Variables: Θ			Design Variables: Θ & h		
		Θ	$h_1:h_2$	\bar{N}	Θ	$h_1:h_2$	\bar{N}
I	10	[40/-45]-s	1:1	36.95	[40/-40]-s	1:2	38.54
	30	[45/-45]-s	1:1	57.17	[45/-45]-s	1:3	62.26
	50	[45/-45]-s	1:1	59.84	[45/-45]-s	1:2	65.43
II	10	[41/-44]-s	1:1	23.72	[41/-41]-s	1:2	24.49
	30	[45/-45]-s	1:1	36.51	[45/-45]-s	1:2	39.52

Table 4. Optimum design of antisymmetrically laminated plates ($a/b=2.0$) for maximum normalized buckling load, $\bar{N}=\bar{N}_1 b^2/E_2 h^3$

Material	$\frac{a}{h}$	Design Variables: Θ			Design Variables: Θ & h		
		Θ	$h_1:h_2$	\bar{N}	Θ	$h_1:h_2$	\bar{N}
I	10	[20/-12]-s	1:1	12.78	[10/-10]-s	1:2	13.00
	30	[31/-42]-s	1:1	50.02	[35/-35]-s	1:3	53.64
	50	[36/-42]-s	1:1	62.96	[39/-39]-s	1:2	68.54
II	10	[19/-23]-s	1:1	9.50	[19/-23]-s	1:2	9.83
	30	[33/-33]-s	1:1	32.66	[32/-32]-s	1:2	34.78